

Deliverable 7.4

Ethical and Legal Management Plan

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● Project Executive Summary

The EU-funded 'Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment' (PHOEBE) project aims to develop an integrated, dynamic human-centred predictive safety assessment framework in urban areas. This will be achieved by bringing together the interdisciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, mode shift and induced demand modelling and new and emerging mobility data.

Focused on vulnerable road users' safety, the 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will draw inspiration from real-world scenarios in the three pilot cities of Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK). Testing activities will be performed across the use cases to simulate and forecast the impact of changes on safety in different scenarios of disruptions or transitions across urban transport networks.

Predicting and visualising the safety and socioeconomic outcomes of new forms of transport, new technologies, or regulatory and behavioural changes from the individual (micro) level up to the network-wide (macro) level will also be a significant game-changer for urban stakeholders. The results of PHOEBE can be used as a blueprint by other European cities to develop their knowledge products, such as socioeconomic analysis model, urban road safety assessment, human behaviour and choice modelling.

● PHOEBE pilot cities

List of participating cities:

- Athens (Greece)
- Valencia (Spain)
- West Midlands (United Kingdom)

Social Links:

 https://twitter.com/Project_PHOEBE

 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>

 <https://www.youtube.com/@phoebeproject>

For further information please visit WWW.PHOEBE-PROJECT.EU

- **Project Partners**

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
EVROPSKI INSTITUT ZA OCENJEVANJE CEST - EURORAP	SI	EIRA
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL	NTUA
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	NL	TUD
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE	TUM
AIMSUN SLU	ES	AIM
POLIS AISBL	BE	POLIS
FACTUAL CONSULTING SL	ES	FC
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	UPV
OSEVEN SINGLE MEMBER PRIVATE COMPANY	EL	O7
THE FLOW LIMITED	UK	FLOW
INTERNATIONAL ROAD ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME	UK	iRAP

- **List of abbreviations and acronyms**

Acronym	Meaning
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
DPA	Data Protection Act 2018 (UK)
IPR	Intellectual property rights
EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EM	Ethics Manager
ET	Ethics Team
IF	Incidental Findings
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PbD	Privacy by Design
R&D	Research and Development
SI	Sensitive
ISO9001	International Standards Organisation – Quality Management
ISO26000	International Standards Organisation – Social Responsibility
ISO27001	International Standards Organisation – Data Security
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
DMP	Data management plan
DMPTask	Data management plan task area
WP	Work package
D	Deliverable

Table of Contents

Contents

• Project Executive Summary	4
• PHOEBE pilot cities	4
• Project Partners	5
• List of abbreviations and acronyms	6
Deliverable executive summary	9
1 Introduction	10
a. Ethical Principles	10
b. Horizon Europe Ethical process	11
c. General Ethical Principles	11
i. The declaration of Helsinki (2013 - latest revision)	11
ii. ISO26000 and social responsibility.	13
d. Horizon Europe Ethical Principles	13
i. Article 19 Regulation 1291/2013 (Horizon Europe)	14
ii. Article 14 Grant Agreement (PHOEBE 101076963)	15
iii. Annex 5 Grant Agreement (PHOEBE 101076963)	15
e. The PHOEBE project and its ethical management	16
i. Ethical management	16
f. Ethical Management Plan review areas	19
i. Ethical Management Plan review area – activity areas	19
ii. Ethical Management Plan review area – deliverables	20
g. Ethical Management Plan review area – Specific tasks	22
h. Data Aspects	22
i. Risk Aspects	22
2) Appendix A - ISO 26000 ethical management consideration areas	23

List of figures

Figure 1 - The PHOEBE structure including the Ethical Board	17
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List of tables

Table 1 - Article 19 - ethical principals	14
Table 2 - Article 14 - Ethics and Values	15
Table 3 - Annex 5 (Ethics and Research Integrity)	16
Table 4 - The appointed members by organisation of the PHOEBE project ethical board	18
Table 5 - Extract from live ethical and legal review register template - PART ONE (review area)	18
Table 6 - Extract from live ethical and legal review register template - PART ONE (review details)	19
Table 7 - Legal areas considered in the project to ensure following the rule of law in project activity.	20

Deliverable executive summary

The PHOEBE Ethical and Legal Management Plan (EMP) satisfies Deliverable 7.4 (D7.4) for the PHOEBE project (agreement number 101076963). This deliverable provides the first version of the EMP which will be reviewed and updated as needed in project delivery (working document). This deliverable describes how the PHOEBE project will manage ethical management within the project.

The EMP furthermore provides information about related deliverables that help to ensure continuous improvement and monitoring of the DMP and data management practices in and beyond the project.

LIVE DOCUMENT

Please note the Ethical and Legal Management Plan is a LIVE document so is subject to continuous improvements. This document may be updated periodically so as to present the best view of ethical and legal management as evolution may occur during the work of the project.

1 Introduction

The scope of the first version of the PHOEBE Ethical and Legal Management Plan (EMP) is to detail ethical and legal principles and define how they will be followed to facilitate sound ethical and legal management both within and beyond the project to best ensure legal adherence and positive ethical impacts from the investigative and project work.

a. Ethical Principles

Fundamental ethical principles apply to all areas of life including scientific research. This is essential to ensure ethical protections for subjects involved in or impacted by research work. Four key ethical pillars are followed:

- Autonomy – respect for individual rights to self-determination;
- Beneficence – the duty to ‘do good’;
- Non-Maleficence – the duty to ‘not do bad;’
- Justice – treat all people equally and equitably

However in any investigative program impacts in the above areas may be unforeseen so means to evaluate impacts and manage ethics are required throughout project operations. Although researchers may face barriers to optimal scientific research, ethical principles and management are there to safeguard the rigidity of research activities and strengthen the willingness of subjects and citizens to participate in or benefit from research activities.

The European Commission interprets research ethics into a collaborative and constructive ongoing process where researchers are asked to consider ethics not only at the conceptual stage of the proposal but also throughout operation with an aim to enhance overall research quality and positive societal impact.

The ‘Golden Rule’ of Ethical Research alongside other good practice principles are endorsed to highlight key ethical principles that will be considered in this project. These ethical principles are:

- Respect the integrity and dignity of all persons equally and equitably.
- Follow “Do Good” and “Do no harm” principles.
- Potential risks must be clearly communicated to any subjects involved or users of project outputs.
- Recognise the rights of all individuals to privacy, personal data protection.
- Recognise the rights and equality of all individuals in freedom of movement.
- Honour requirements for informed consent and continuous dialogue with any research subjects.
- Respect the principle of proportionality: not imposing more than is necessary on subjects or going beyond stated purposes.
- Respect the environment and do not impose or encourage change that threaten the environment or ecological balance.
- Build on the understanding that project benefits are for the good of society, and any shared expressions of concern about threats from your research must be considered.

These high-level ethical principles are supported by ethical processes and guidance from several sources. These include the formal frameworks of Horizon Europe which are now detailed.

b. Horizon Europe Ethical process

Horizon Europe projects include specific frameworks to guide the handling of ethical management each designed to support relevant project phases. These are:

1. **Ethics Self-assessment** (upon application submission - complete)
2. **Ethics Review** (prior to the finalisation of the Grant Agreement initiated by the EU Commission)
 - a. Ethics Pre-screening (complete)
 - b. Ethics Screening (complete)
 - c. Ethics Assessment (complete)
3. **Ethics Check and Ethics Audit** (ongoing and the focus of this EMP document to maintain ongoing ethical management during and after project execution)

The remainder of this document focuses upon the third point and ongoing management within the project operation and its ongoing impacts.

c. General Ethical Principles

Before detailing ethics checks and processes it is vital to clarify the ethical principles they seek to support. Ethical principles however have many definitions and of these the PHOEBE project seeks to follow those considered as best ethical practice across these. Although many ethical guidance principles exist (all with common aims) the PHOEBE project makes specific mention of two key principles. These are detailed below:

i. The declaration of Helsinki (2013 - latest revision)

The Declaration of Helsinki is a highly influential set of ethical principles regarding human involvement in experimentation and although devised for medical experimentation it is still regarded as a foundational and guiding part for **all** modern research ethics. This declaration is not law but it (and its revisions) remains a guiding principle and widely adopted to investigative work seeking to protect individuals. This declaration states via a number of articles each detailing fundamental ethical rights of research participants and constraints for research to ensure ethical handling relating to research. All PHOEBE partners and investigators will follow these articles. These articles include:

- The fundamental principle of respect for individuals (Article 8).
 - The PHOEBE project seeks to uphold and not undermine Article 8 principles.
- The right to self-determination (Article 20)
 - The PHOEBE project does not seek to remove rights to self-determination rather it intends to lower barriers for wider consideration of mobility modes supporting better self-determination regarding the fundamental right to mobility.
- The right to make informed decisions (Articles 21 and 22) regarding participation in research activities with specific consent given, both initially and during any research.

- o Any external participants in focus groups stakeholders will have informed consent in engagement in the research process. This will be administered by the research task leaders or organisations engaging external research participants.
- Recognition of the vulnerability of specific individuals or groups (Article 8) and need for specific handling for research participants incapable of giving informed consent, or is a minor (Articles 23, 24).
 - o The PHOEBE project will consider risk in relation to vulnerable road users and groups - such as the young in the presence of schools and playgrounds. Specific engagement of research participants from vulnerable groups will be considered in external and public information gathering.
- Investigators have a duty to research participants (Articles 2, 3 and 10) meaning the participant's welfare must always take precedence over the interests of the scientific research (Article 5).
 - o PHOEBE researchers will prioritise the rights of participants over the desire for project aims in all external contact.
- Research must be based on a thorough knowledge of the scientific background (Article 11)
 - o WP1 activity provides systematic reviews of areas of science relevant to the project to ensure the criteria for Article 11 is followed in ongoing work.
- Researchers must carefully consider assessment of risks and benefits (Articles 16, 17) before undertaking activity and have a reasonable likelihood of benefit to society or sections of it studied (Article 19).
 - o The PHOEBE project has a dedicated risk management activity (T7.3) to ensure such protections as well as data management plans (D7.2) to ensure protection of individuals privacy and data.
- Research must be conducted by suitably trained investigators (Article 15) using approved protocols, subject to ethical review and oversight by a properly convened committee (Article 13).
 - o The PHOEBE project is supported with skilled and selected staffing to provide leading expertise to scientific areas of investigation such that ethical handling is considered and follows best practices.
- Studies should be discontinued if the newly available information indicates that the original considerations are no longer satisfied and ethical impacts are found (Article 17).
 - o The PHOEBE project has continuous reviews of activity covering, risk, data management and ethics, these efforts protect article 17.
- Information regarding the study should be made as publicly available as possible to ensure societal benefit (Article 16).
 - o The aspects of the project related to 1) dissemination (WP6) and 2) data management (D7.2) aim to ensure 'FAIR' data principles (see D7.2 for details) these seek to directly support Article 16.
- Ethical principles extend to dissemination of results including consideration of any potential conflict of interest (Article 27)
 - o WP6 activities help to consider and support well principled releases about the project activity with consideration of any potential conflicts of interest or ethical impacts for any public information release.
- Research methodologies should be compared against alternative methods (Article 29) to highlight effectiveness.

- The scientific approaches in WP3/4/5 and the Evaluation within these ensure a scientific basis in results to adhere to article 29. WP1 also helps background state of the art to ensure adequate comparisons are used.
- The interests of any participant after any study is completed should be considered to ensure no negative impacts (Article 30).
 - The protection of personal details related to individuals remains after the project end as does accountability to the impacts of the work with the participants. To assure positive impacts in the body of research stakeholder engagement and input ensures outputs support article 30.
- Unproven methods should be tested only in the context of research where there is reasonable belief of possible benefit and no risk of harm (Article 32).
 - Continuous ethical and work package activity reviews throughout the life of the project provide means to approve and review work as they happen to minimise any risk of harm (article 32).

Ethical review principles covering all areas of the declaration of Helsinki are embedded into PHOEBE ethical management.

ii. ISO26000 and social responsibility.

ISO 26000 is a standardised approach for controlled management of social impacts based around seven core principles. This global standards-based approach seeks to formalise ethical management practices to ensure key areas in ethical management are factored into decision making, reporting and monitoring. These form seven key principles and consideration of them in decision and review processes to: operationalise a fixed approach for ethical management and promote processes that improve ethical management and responsibility.

The seven core principles detail management consideration areas for ethical decision making, these are:

- Accountability.
- Transparency.
- Ethical behaviour.
- Respect for stakeholder interests.
- Respect for the rule of law.
- Respect for international norms of behaviour.
- Respect for human rights.

These aspects cover similar aims to the declaration of helsinki (above) but fix the regions to which considerations must be evaluated against. Within PHOEBE the consideration areas declared in ISO 26000 support ethical reviews by providing listed review areas within ethical management. They are formally specified in Clause 6 of the ISO 2600 standard which breaks down into a larger list of consideration topics for ethical management. These specific clause areas are listed in more detail in appendix A for reference and reuse in project ethical reviews which check against these areas. The usage of these areas is detailed later in this document.

d. Horizon Europe Ethical Principles

To further help standardise ethical handling in Horizon Europe (HE) projects good practice terms are incorporated into agreement articles and terms that clearly detail high level ethical principles

that should be followed. PHOEBE follows these principles. These ‘HE’ principles are detailed in three key areas:

1. Article 19 1291/2013 - Regulation gives specific guidance for ethical principles that awarded projects should follow.
2. PHOEBE Grant agreement article 14 - Ethics and values
3. PHOEBE Grant agreement annex 5 - Ethics and Research Integrity and Gender mainstream values

Each of these three sets of ethical principles are separately detailed below with outline relevance to the project aims:

i. Article 19 Regulation 1291/2013 (Horizon Europe)

These terms within the framework program Horizon Europe terms detail high level ethical principles aimed at the pre-grant stage for where projects can and cannot be ethically accepted for funding. These aspects in particular steer the pre acceptance ethics review process. These are detailed in full below.

Article 19 ethical principles

1. All the research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon Europe shall comply with ethical principles and relevant national, Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols.

Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

2. Research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon Europe shall have an exclusive focus on civil applications.

3. The following fields of research shall not be financed:

(a) research activity aiming at human cloning for reproductive purposes;

(b) research activity intended to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such changes heritable);

(c) research activities intended to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

4. Research on human stem cells, both adult and embryonic, may be financed, depending both on the contents of the scientific proposal and the legal framework of the Member States involved. No funding shall be granted for research activities that are prohibited in all the Member States. No activity shall be funded in a Member State where such activity is forbidden.

5. The fields of research set out in paragraph 3 of this Article may be reviewed within the context of the interim evaluation set out in Article 32(3) in the light of scientific advances.

Table 1 - Article 19 - ethical principals

PHOEBE has many areas in these outline terms that do not apply to this program of research, namely, non civil (military) applications, cloning, stem cells, genetic and human embryos. Beyond these areas the project plan directly ensures means to proactively address the listed areas, for instance allocation of planned expertise and continuous monitoring for data management. This is continuously tracked in the Data Management Plan (D7.2) which relates to the ethical management plan in the PHOEBE project. Wider aspects of ethical control are included in the project also to aim to ensure positive ethical operation and impacts from the work, these are detailed more fully later in this document.

ii. Article 14 Grant Agreement (PHOEBE 101076963)

These terms supporting ethical processes are more specifically targeted directly within the PHOEBE project grant agreement which have been accepted by all partner organisations. These agreement requirements are detailed at high level in article 14 of the grant agreement (grant agreement number 101076963). These terms are detailed below also:

ARTICLE 14 — ETHICS AND VALUES

14.1 Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. Specific ethics rules (if any) are set out in Annex 5.

14.2 Values

The beneficiaries must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities). Specific rules on values (if any) are set out in Annex 5.

14.3 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 28).

Table 2 - Article 14 - Ethics and Values

These agreement terms detail the high level ethical principles the project should adhere to. The specifics however are detailed more fully in the same document in Annex 5 (see below).

iii. Annex 5 Grant Agreement (PHOEBE 101076963)

Annex 5 of the grant agreement provides additional ethical principles terms for the PHOEBE project applicable to all project partners. These terms are detailed in full below:

Annex 5 (of the phoebe grant agreement)

Ethics and research integrity

The beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with:

- *ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity)*
- *applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.*

No funding can be granted, within or outside the EU, for activities that are prohibited in all Member States. No funding can be granted in a Member State for an activity which is forbidden in that Member State.

The beneficiaries must pay particular attention to the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of persons, the right to non-discrimination, the need to ensure protection of the environment and high levels of human health protection.

The beneficiaries must ensure that the activities under the action have an exclusive focus on civil applications.

The beneficiaries must ensure that the activities under the action do not:

- *aim at human cloning for reproductive purposes*
- *intend to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such modifications heritable (with the exception of research relating to cancer treatment of the gonads, which may be financed)*

- *intend to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer, or*
- *lead to the destruction of human embryos (for example, for obtaining stem cells).*

Activities involving research on human embryos or human embryonic stem cells may be carried out only if:

- *they are set out in Annex 1 or*
- *the coordinator has obtained explicit approval (in writing) from the granting authority.*

In addition, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity — as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

This implies compliance with the following principles:

- *reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources*
- *honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way*
- *respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment*
- *accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices including ensuring, where possible, openness, reproducibility and traceability and refrain from the research integrity violations described in the Code.*
- *Activities raising ethical issues must comply with the additional requirements formulated by the ethics panels (including after checks, reviews or audits; see Article 25).*

Before starting an action task raising ethical issues, the beneficiaries must have obtained all approvals or other mandatory documents needed for implementing the task, notably from any (national or local) ethics committee or other bodies such as data protection authorities.

The documents must be kept on file and be submitted upon request by the coordinator to the granting authority. If they are not in English, they must be submitted together with an English summary, which shows that the documents cover the action tasks in question and includes the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned (if any).

VALUES (— ARTICLE 14)

Gender mainstreaming

The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

Table 3 - Annex 5 (Ethics and Research Integrity)

Not all the above article terms (like those in the framework agreement Article 19, see above) are relevant to the PHOEBE project scope. For instance the focus remains on civil application without any aspects of cloning, stem cells, embryo or genetic research. These terms however do provide clear high level guidance for ethical data management related to the project. The key aspects of this are detailed in the following section of this document.

e. The PHOEBE project and its ethical management

The PHOEBE project is funded by the European Commission (EC) to advance risk assessment frameworks and models for urban roads. The project focuses its investigative work, development and evaluation within three use case regions; Athens (Greece), Valencia (Spain) and The West Midlands (United Kingdom). Within each region (and at times beyond) tasks undertaken and resultant outputs may need ethical consideration, review and record keeping. For review an approach of ethical management must be considered.

i. Ethical management

Ethical management for the project as a whole requires a defined process and clear definitions to understand aspects of: responsibility, management, audience, notification, update and process. These are now each detailed:

RESPONSIBILITY

Ethical management within PHOEBE is the responsibility of **ALL** partners and **ALL** participants. Each partner separately agrees by the terms of the grant agreement to follow ethical principles (detailed above and in appendices) throughout the project activities for all involved staff. For this all ethical reviews will be assigned ownership to the manager of each task.

MANAGEMENT

Within the project to support coordinated ethical management specific means have been planned and put in place to ensure ethical management and review. This is supported by the formation of a specific ethical board which provides interaction with the steering committee, the partner organisations and the granting authority.

Figure 1 - The PHOEBE structure including the Ethical Board

The ethical board provides a managerial level of review for ethical and legal management that are reported and discussed in steering committee meetings or reported directly from partner organisations (with each being separately accountable for its ethical management as per the grant agreement terms).

This is coordinated by a chair (Sam Chapman from The Floow) and a principal named person from each other organisation to ensure full project coverage including all partners for ongoing ethical management.

Organisation	Ethical Board Member appointed	
	Name	Surname
The Floow (CHAIR)	Sam	Chapman
iRAP	Andejus	Laugman
AIMSUN	Mark	Brackstone
EIRA	Marko	Sevrovic
TUM	Christelle	Al Haddad
UPV	Ana María	Pérez-Zuriaga
OSeven	Petros	Fortsakis
NTUA	George Yannis	NTUA
POLIS	Pedro	de Gouveia
FC	Stefania	Pesavento
TUD	Eleonora	Papadimitriou

Table 4 - The appointed members by organisation of the PHOEBE project ethical board

Any Ethical reviews or issues (and if occurring any legal issues) related to the project will be recorded, analysed and documented in an Ethical and Legal Manual (spreadsheet register maintained throughout the project - this is detailed later in this document). This supports capture, review and record keeping for any ethical issues that may arise. For each item the ethical and legal register lists the responsible owner of each review item as well as details about its status, its ISO26000 considered areas (see above) and its overall ethical review determination. The Ethical Board (composed of all consortium partners) is responsible to ensure revision, approval, and application of the legal and ethical requirements for the project. As well as meeting standing items in the steering committee the ethical board will convene separately to review and update processes and mechanisms a minimum of annually.

AUDIENCE: The intended target for the EMP is primarily all project partners to ensure good practice data handling and ethical compliance through the project. This is however a public document and may be viewed by wider stakeholders or other parties as needed.

NOTIFICATION: Each partner **must** notify the ethics board regarding any changes in tasks or plans that require review to maintain up to date ethical management reviews and records. To support this a standing item for ethical management has been added to quarterly work package leader reviews.

UPDATE: Any changes in ethics, activity or good practice may in the future update this document and the overall ethical management plan or its supporting registers to support required refinement to the project ethical handling as the project progresses. These documents are considered live throughout the remainder of the project.

PROCESS: To standardise the way in which ethical reviews are undertaken and recorded a fixed process for how they are handled is followed. This uses an Ethical and Legal review Register [**LIVE DOCUMENT**] containing the following details:

OWNER	WP / TASK RELATED	ITEM	DETAILS	TYPE	STATUS
This lists the ethical review OWNER. This will often be reviewed by wider members of the ethical board but the OWNER remains the principal contact and responsible individual	This details areas of work by workpackage (WP) or tasks (T) areas that the ethics applies to.	This is a high level title of the ethics item considered.	This is a detailed description of the ethical consideration area detailing its scope of coverage.	These come in three types relating to the type of review. These are: 1) ACTIVITY AREAS 2) SPECIFIC TASKS 3) DELIVERABLES	This details the status of the review - if PENDING (yet to occur), OPEN (subject to ongoing refinement or review), CLOSED (with a date the review was closed)

Table 5 - Extract from live ethical and legal review register template - PART ONE (review area)

Ethical areas (following ISO 26000 review principles) considerations							ETHICAL DETERMINATION AFTER REVIEW
Accountability.	Transparency.	Ethical behaviour.	Respect for stakeholder interests.	Respect for the rule of law.	Respect for international norms of behaviour.	Respect for human rights.	
This details the accountability related to the ethical area under review. This may be different to the OWNER.	This details the transparency of the activity prioritising OPEN and FAIR inclusion in the activity	This seeks to capture the ethical behaviour related to the review area and encourages good practice.	This encourages alignment of activity to stakeholder interests and reviews how the area may impact such interests.	This details how the activity follows relevant laws ensuring not just ethical but also legal handling related to the review area.	This details following good practice and established norms to demonstrate how the review fits into existing environments	This details how the area could impact in terms of fundamental rights including equality, inclusion, diversity and other fundamental human rights.	Following the areas of review this summarises ethical review that has been undertaken by those involved or feedback from the ethical board.

Table 6 - Extract from live ethical and legal review register template - PART ONE (review details)

This register is available to the project team and reviewers and when needed extracts each related to separated tasks may be provided to relevant stakeholders.

The above template requires consideration and recording of tasks adherence to the rule of law. For the sake of the project a list of all laws in all operating countries would be prohibitive however key legal areas to consider are presented that the project must consider in any review.

Law and legal areas	Details
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Data Protection, storage, processing and personal data regulation	Seeking to protect the use of data related to individuals. This includes GDPR (2016/679), but also national laws, such as UK's Data Protection Act 2018 and related legislation related to personal data control, consent, transfer, rights to access and correction. Please note that this area is handled more directly in D7.2 Data Management Plan.
Intellectual property and copyright law	Respecting the rights of intellectual property owners, following international trademark, design, copyright and patent law.
Confidentiality and disclosure protection	Respecting confidentiality and protected data as per the collaboration agreement terms between partners or external agents agreements in particular with respect to background and foreground IP or otherwise protected data.
Licenses and rights of use	Respecting third party data and restrictions that may apply from declared license or agreement for access.
Gender, race and other equality law	To protect stakeholders and participants in terms of special category data usage.
Environmental Legislation	To ensure project activity complies with and does no avoidable harm to the environment in the course of the project work.
Health and Safety	To ensure the protection of researchers, citizens and stakeholders in connection to the project work.

Table 7 - Legal areas considered in the project to ensure following the rule of law in project activity.

It should be recalled by partners despite these considerations and checks that each organisation is separately accountable for its own legal compliance.

f. Ethical Management Plan review areas

To support these ethical reviews the PHOEBE project will consider reviews in three review areas:

1. **Activity areas.**
2. **Deliverables.**
3. **Specific Tasks.**

These are each now detailed:

i. Ethical Management Plan review area – activity areas

Activity areas concern the broad function areas of project activity and are each separately reviewed at a high level. This review although high level simply helps to ensure planned activity areas support high level legal and ethical objectives and not just project delivery. This ensures a

high-level overarching review to ensure the broad project aims and its parts remain legal and ethical.

These high-level reviews cover the following principal areas:

- Processing of partner information, mailing lists, and external contacts for project coordination.
- ATHENS - Stakeholder mapping and handling of data around use case and citizens.
- VALENCIA - Stakeholder mapping and handling of data around use case and citizens.
- WESTMIDLANDS(UK) - Stakeholder mapping and handling of data around use case and citizens.
- CONSUMER - Data exploration and records of data resource needs to fit needs of requirements.
- PRODUCERS - Data exploration and records of data resource needs to fit needs of requirements.
- CONSUMER - Data collation to fit needs of requirements.
- PRODUCER - Data provision to fit needs of requirements.
- ATHENS - Project data creation/gathering by new means.
- VALENCIA - Project data creation/gathering by new means.
- WESTMIDLANDS(UK) - Project data creation/gathering by new means.
- Processing to filter data for project use.
- Processing to reformat data for fixed format project use.
- Measurement analysis and scientific verification of work.
- Output data and risk related measurements or recommendations.
- Dissemination of project results.

Each of these have a full ethical review and are included in the projects Ethical and Legal Review Register.

ii. Ethical Management Plan review area – deliverables

To support the delivery and aligned working in the project for the EMP to be successful each deliverable is reviewed to detail aspects that will likely require the potential of an ethical review. These are each detailed with each associated responsible partner responsible for ethical handling and ethical review areas.

Deliverable Identifier	Title of deliverable	Responsible Partner	Description of deliverable and its connection and support to the EMP and its continuous implementation and refinement in the project
D1.1	SoA and end user needs review	TUD	This deliverable explores related literature and state of the art that may inform wider ethical impacts for the working area from related work. It also reports on the work of focus groups, stakeholder connections and surveys; all such external interactions require ethical review.
D1.2	Theoretical principles and methodological approaches of the PHOEBE framework and selection of tools	TUD	This deliverable explores the selection of tools and methodologies for the research activity. As such any selection of tools must consider ethical impacts so will be considered via review to consider its ethical impacts.

D2.1	Consolidated data requirements and use case region data availability report	FLOOW	This deliverable and its sub tasks collate and manages data requirements for which each data area and its processing should be considered for ethical handling. This review will be linked to the Data Management Plan DMP which is closely tied and also considers ethics.
D2.2	Data register, feature report and accreditation	FLOOW	This details available data and seeks to encourage FAIR principles according to the Data Management plan DMP.
D3.1	New and enhanced models/simulation environments and user support materials (Beta ed.)	iRAP	This deliverable and its related tasks need to consider ethical impacts of new models and guidance given to the imp[acts from them upon wider society. Ethical review needs to consider these developments and how tools will be utilised with the potential to impact peoples lives.
D3.2	Finalised models/simulation environments methodology factsheets and user support materials	iRAP	As above, this deliverable and its related tasks need to consider potential impacts from refined models and guidance so as to ensure societally beneficial outputs.
D4.1	Use case experimental designs	EIRA	This deliverable and its tasks concerns real world experimental design with the potential to impact or influence stakeholders or citizens within test scenarios. This clearly needs to consider project ethical principles including those of the declaration of helsinki articles via an ethical review. This seeks to ensure that experiments have ethically positive investigation and outputs.
D4.2	Consolidated use case evaluation and assessment report	EIRA	The ethical principles of evaluation and assessment require ethical review.
D5.1	Consolidated PHOEBE framework methodology, network-level demonstration results and tools	NTUA	The demonstration framework is a principal project output that has ability to influence decision making or society from its impacts. As such the target is subjected to ethical review to ensure positive outputs form the resulting framework.
D5.2	User interface and implementation	POLIS	The user interface aspects in the project work direct connect to end users and encourage particular interactions with impacts and effects. As such this requires an ethical review to ensure this follows ethical principles detailed in this document.
D6.1	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan	POLIS	This details how information may be shared with wider individuals, communities or organisations as such the impact must be considered for these via an ethical review.
D6.2	Final exploitation, IPR and replication plans	FC	This details exploitation plans, registers and materials that require management. This

			supports the EMP to ensure controller and beneficial outputs for the project are shared to selected audiences. This process and activity requires an ethical management plan.
D7.1	Project Management Handbook	iRAP	This defines operating management for the project including FAIR principles for public facing documents as such this requires ethical review to ensure the project targets societally beneficial impacts.
D7.2	Data Management Plan	FLOOW	The data management plan has been developed to consider ethical implications from data alongside its gathering and management. The Data Management Plan (DMP) is strongly connected to this work as such it includes an ethical review..
D7.4	Ethics Management Plan	FLOOW	This document (EMP)

Table 4 - Ethical Management Plan related Deliverables that support continuous delivery according to the Ethical Management Plan

These reviews may be added throughout the project with all included in the projects Ethical and Legal Review Register.

g. Ethical Management Plan review area – Specific tasks

These allow focus on specific project activities that by themselves may need individualised review (for example when making and releasing new public facing surveys ethics for the recipients must be individually considered). These aspects of review may be added throughout the project with all included in the projects Ethical and Legal Review Register.

h. Data Aspects

A strong aspect of ethical management relates to data management, in particular, for how data is gathered stored and handled this area of ethical management is detailed separately in the project Data Management Plan (D7.2.) which also considers ethics related to data. This document is also subject to continuous update, and should be considered alongside the Ethical Management Plan.

i. Risk Aspects

Risk management may also be related to ethical management and is handled throughout the project and as such it may contain ethical risks. These if required will be captured in the project risk register (D7.1) should they emerge.

2) Appendix A - ISO 26000 ethical management consideration areas

This appendix lists ethical management consideration areas detailed in the ISO 26000 standard. This list is presented merely as guidance to consider related to the ethical review areas. For any review reviewers are asked to consider all these areas within scope of review.

Core subject: Organizational governance, subclause 6.2

Decisions are to be made in consideration of the expectations of society. Accountability, transparency, ethics, and stakeholders should be factors in the organisation's decision-making process.

Core subject: Human rights, subclause 6.3

All humans have the right to fair treatment and the elimination of discrimination, torture, and exploitation.

- 6.3.3 Due diligence
- 6.3.4 Human rights risk situations
- 6.3.5 Avoidance of complicity
- 6.3.6 Resolving grievances
- 6.3.7 Discrimination and vulnerable groups
- 6.3.8 Civil and political rights
- 6.3.9 Economic, social, and cultural rights
- 6.3.10 Fundamental principles and rights at work

Core subject: Labor practices, subclause 6.4

Those working on behalf of any organisation are not a commodity. The goal is to prevent unfair competition based on exploitation and abuse.

- 6.4.3 Employment and employment relationships
- 6.4.4 Conditions of work and social protection
- 6.4.5 Social dialogue
- 6.4.6 Health and safety at work
- 6.4.7 Human development and training in the workplace

Core subject: Environment, subclause 6.5

The organisation has a responsibility to reduce and eliminate unsustainable volumes and patterns of production and consumption and to ensure that resource consumption per person becomes sustainable.

- 6.5.3 Prevention of pollution
- 6.5.4 Sustainable resource use
- 6.5.5 Climate change mitigation and adaptation
- 6.5.6 Protection of the environment, biodiversity, and restoration of natural habitats

Core subject: Fair operating practices, subclause 6.6

Building systems of fair competition, preventing corruption, encouraging fair competition, and promoting the reliability of fair business practices help to build sustainable social systems.

- 6.6.3 Anti-corruption
- 6.6.4 Responsible political involvement
- 6.6.5 Fair competition
- 6.6.6 Promoting social responsibility in the value chain
- 6.6.7 Respect for property rights

Core subject: Consumer issues, subclause 6.7

The promotion of just, sustainable, and equitable economic and social development with respect to consumer health, safety, and access is the organisation's responsibility.

- 6.7.3 Fair marketing, factual, and unbiased information and fair contractual practices
- 6.7.4 Protecting consumers' health and safety
- 6.7.5 Sustainable consumption
- 6.7.6 Consumer service, support, and complaint and dispute resolution
- 6.7.7 Consumer data protection and privacy
- 6.7.8 Access to essential services
- 6.7.9 Education and awareness

Core subject: Community involvement and development, subclause 6.8

The organisation should be involved with creating sustainable social structures where increasing levels of education and well-being can exist.

- 6.8.3 Community involvement
- 6.8.4 Education and culture
- 6.8.5 Employment creation and skills development
- 6.8.6 Technology development and access
- 6.8.7 Wealth and income creation
- 6.8.8 Health
- 6.8.9 Social investment

LIVE DOCUMENT

Please note the Ethical and Legal Management Plan is a LIVE document so is subject to continuous improvements. This document may be updated periodically so as to present the best view of ethical and legal management as evolution may occur during the work of the project.